

DEANS' AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOUR AS CORRELATE OF FOSTERING ACADEMIC INTEGRITY AMONG ADMINISTRATIVE HEADS IN LAGOS STATE UNIVERSITIES, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between deans' authentic leadership behaviour and fostering academic integrity among administrative heads in Lagos State Universities, Nigeria. The study hinged on Authentic Leadership theory which provides a framework for deans to demonstrate a genuine, transparent, emotional intelligence and true leadership style in the university. Two research questions were raised and two null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlational design. The population of this study consisted of all Deans and Head of Department in the three state universities owned by the Lagos State government. A sample size of 30 Deans and 90 Heads of Department was simple random sampling technique. Two research instruments titled 'The Deans' Authentic Leadership Behaviour Questionnaire' (DALBQ) and the Heads of Department Academic Integrity Questionnaire' (HDATQ) were used for data collection. The reliability consistency of the instruments was 0.61 and 0.66 coefficient using Cronbach's alpha. Kendall's tau-b correlation was used to analyse data collected via Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23.0. The findings of hypotheses 1, and 2 showed that: a significant relationship existed between deans' transformational leadership behaviour and head of department academic integrity in Lagos State Universities, Nigeria ($\tau_b = .534$; $N=120$; $p<0.05$, and a significant relationship existed between deans emotional intelligent and head of department academic integrity in Lagos State Universities, Nigeria ($\tau_b = .583$; $N=120$; $p<0.05$). Based on the findings, the study concluded that Deans who demonstrate authentic leadership behaviour, such as being genuine, honest, transparent and empathy, are more likely to promote academic integrity among their HODs. It is therefore recommended, amongst others, that faculty Deans should provide leadership training programs that focus on authentic leadership behaviour and promote academic integrity programs through workshops, seminars, symposia and conferences periodically.

Keywords: Academic Integrity, Authentic Leadership, Deans' Behaviour and Universities

Introduction

Today, university education in Nigeria, particularly in Lagos State, faces several issues, including authentic leadership behaviour and academic integrity. Authentic leadership seems to be a leadership style that emphasizes the importance of leaders being genuine, honest, transparent, and self-disciplined in themselves and their values. However, academic integrity is a core value in all higher education institutions globally. Academic dishonesty and corruption are major issues in

many universities, including those in Nigeria. Academic dishonesty has been connected to a variety of causes, including ineffective leadership, weak institutional policies, poor leadership behaviour and lack of responsibility. Furthermore, there is growing worry about the incidence of academic dishonesty among academic staff, and faculty students at Lagos State Universities in Nigeria. Despite efforts by the Lagos State Government to encourage academic integrity in universities, the issue persists. The lack of academic integrity among administrative heads of Lagos State institutions is particularly alarming, as it has the potential to harm the universities' legitimacy and reputation. The issue of academic dishonesty in Nigerian universities is extensively documented.

More so, the National Universities Commission (NUC) discovered that academic dishonesty is a big concern for Nigerian universities (Okebukola, 2017). The analysis found poor leadership, ineffective institutional practices, and a lack of accountability as important contributors to the problem. Academic dishonesty is a major challenge at Lagos State universities. According to a survey conducted by the Lagos State Government, academic dishonesty is rampant among heads of department and faculty members which undermines integrity in Lagos State universities. The university system is plagued by a lack of academic integrity and insufficient leadership from faculty deans and administrative executives. Despite increased concern about academic dishonesty in Nigerian universities, there has been little research into the relationship between Dean's leadership behavior and cultivating academic integrity among administrative heads in Lagos State universities. Dean leadership behaviour is the actions, decisions, and communication styles of Deans, who is a senior academic administrator responsible for leading a faculty, school, or college within a university. Therefore, this study seeks to address a research gap by looking into the relationship between Dean's authentic leadership behaviour and fostering academic integrity among administrative heads at Lagos State Universities.

Statement of the Problem

Stakeholders in higher education have expressed concern about leadership conduct, corrupt practices, misrepresentation, sexual harassment, indiscipline and poor emotional intelligence among Deans of faculties and administrative heads of various departments in the state universities. Academic integrity is a crucial issue in higher education institutions around the world. Academic

dishonesty has been connected to a variety of causes, including a lack of true leadership, ineffective institutional policies, and a lack of responsibility. The National Universities Commission (NUC) has stressed the importance of university administrators and faculty Deans upholding academic integrity and preventing systemic corruption. Academic integrity seems to be a crucial issue in higher education institutions around the world. However, despite these efforts, academic dishonesty and corrupt practices remains a significant challenge in the state-owned universities. Despite the public outcry about academic dishonesty in Nigerian universities, there is a dearth of research on the relationship between Deans' authentic leadership behaviour and fostering academic integrity among administrative heads in Lagos State universities. Deans' authentic leadership behaviour has been identified as a critical factor in promoting academic integrity in universities. This study aims to fill this research gap by investigating the relationship between Deans' authentic leadership behavior and fostering academic integrity among administrative heads in Lagos State universities.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study was to:

1. Examine the relationship between deans' authentic leadership behaviour and head of department academic integrity in Lagos State Universities, Nigeria.
2. Determine the relationship between deans' emotional intelligence and heads of department academic integrity in Lagos State Universities, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were raised:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between deans' authentic leadership behaviour and head of department academic integrity in Lagos State Universities, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between deans' emotional intelligence and heads of department academic integrity in Lagos State Universities, Nigeria.

Literature Review

The conceptual framework suggests that Deans' leadership behaviour is a critical factor in promoting academic integrity among administrative Heads in Lagos State universities. The framework also suggests that institutional policies and procedures, as well as organizational culture, can moderate the relationship between Deans' leadership behaviour and fostering academic integrity. The study is anchored on the Authentic leadership theory developed by Bill George (2003). The theory emphasizes the importance of leaders being genuine, transparent, and true to themselves and their values. According to George, authentic leaders demonstrate self-disciplined, a strong moral code, and a willingness to take risks and be vulnerable. The authentic leadership approach emphasizes the importance of leaders being honest, genuine, transparent, self-discipline and true to themselves and their values. Authentic leadership is an approach that emphasizes a leader's legitimacy through honest relationships with followers who value their input and are built on an ethical foundation (Gardner et al. in Mohammed, Shittu & Lawal, 2019); it is based on trust, credibility, integrity and adherence to ethical and moral principles (Morales and Santaolalla, 2013). It is positively related to work attitudes and behaviorus (Ozkan and Ceylan, 2016).

Deans' leadership behaviour refers to the actions and behaviours exhibited by Deans in leading and managing academic programs in universities. The components of dean authentic leadership include self-awareness, transparency, ethical behaviour, emotional intelligence, honesty and vulnerability to promote academic integrity. The conceptual framework suggests that Deans' leadership behavior is a critical factor in promoting academic integrity among administrative heads in Lagos State universities. The framework also suggests that institutional policies and procedures, as well as organizational culture, can moderate the relationship between Deans' leadership behavior and fostering academic integrity. However, academic integrity is essential in academic institutions as it maintains the credibility and validity of academic research and credentials, fosters a fair and honest learning environment, encourages original thought and intellectual curiosity, and prepares students for professional life, where ethical behaviour is crucial. Academic integrity is the commitment to uphold the values of honesty, trust, and responsibility in academic pursuits. Academic integrity is compromised when individuals engage in behaviours such as Plagiarism, cheating, fabrication, collusion and misrepresentation. Universities can promote establishing clear policies and procedures, educating students and faculty about academic integrity, encouraging a

culture of honesty and responsibility, providing support and resources for students, and addressing and penalising academic integrity violations. The Deans authentic leadership behaviour has been identified as a critical factor in promoting academic integrity in universities. Moreover, there is a dearth of research on the relationship between Dean's leadership behaviour and fostering academic integrity among administrative heads in Lagos State universities.

Methodology

The study adopted correlational design. The population of this study consisted of all Deans and Head of Department in the three state universities owned by the Lagos State government. A sample size of 30 Deans and 90 Heads of Department was selected through a simple random sampling technique. Two research instruments titled 'The Deans' Authentic Leadership Behaviour Questionnaire' (DALBQ) and the 'Heads of Department Academic Integrity Questionnaire' (HDATQ) were used for data collection. 30 Academic and Non-Academic Heads of department and 10 deans of faculties were selected for the study from each of the three state-owned universities: Lagos State University (LASU), Lagos State University of Education (LASUED) and Lagos State University of Science and Technology (LASUSTECH) in Lagos State. The questionnaire is divided into two sections: Section A and B. Section A contains the personal information of the respondents and Section B contains the 20 items structured around the research questions. Each statement is measured on a four-point modifier Likert-type-rating scale, namely: "Strongly Agree (SA)", "Agree (A)", "Strongly Disagree (SD)", and "Disagree (D)". The Content validity of the instruments was ensured by test experts, and the reliability consistency of the instruments was 0.61 and 0.66 coefficient using Cronbach's The data collected were analysed using Kendall's tau-b correlation coefficient through the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 23.0

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Kendall's tau-b correlation analysis between deans' authentic leadership behaviour and head of department academic integrity in Lagos State Universities, Nigeria

Variables	Correlations	
	Deans' Leadership Behaviour	Authentic Head of Department Academic Integrity

Kendall's tau_b	Deans' Authentic Leadership Behaviour	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.534
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
		N	120	120
	Head_of_Department Academic Integrity	Correlation Coefficient	.534	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
		N	120	120

Source: Field Survey (2024)* Correlation was significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

A Kendall's tau-b correlation was run to investigate the relationship between deans' authentic leadership behaviour and head of department academic integrity in Lagos State Universities, Nigeria. The result indicated that there was a strong, positive correlation relationship between deans' authentic leadership behaviour and head of department academic integrity which was statistically significant ($\tau_b = .534; N=120; p<0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that "there is no significant relationship between deans' authentic leadership behaviour and head of department academic integrity in Lagos State Universities, Nigeria is rejected and an alternate was accepted. The p-value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 significance level which indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis. The results indicate that a statistically, significant relationship existed between deans' authentic leadership behaviour and head of department academic integrity at Lagos State Universities, Nigeria. The findings of this study are in line with Okebukola (2017) found that Deans' leadership behavior is a significant predictor of academic integrity among administrative heads in Nigerian universities. The study identified transformational leadership behavior as a key factor in promoting academic integrity in Nigerian universities.

Table 2: Kendall's tau-b correlation analysis between deans' emotional intelligence and head of department academic integrity in Lagos State Universities, Nigeria

Variables	Correlations			
		Deans' Emotional Intelligence	Head of Department Academic Integrity	
Kendall's tau_b	Deans' Emotional Intelligence	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.583
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
		N	120	120
	Head_of_Department Academic Integrity	Correlation Coefficient	.583	1.000

Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
N	120	120

Source: Field Survey (2024)* Correlation was significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

A Kendall's tau-b correlation was run to investigate the relationship between deans' emotional intelligence and head of department academic integrity at Lagos State Universities, Nigeria. The result indicated that there was a strong, positive correlation relationship between deans' emotional intelligence which was statistically significant ($\tau_b = .583; N=120; p<.05$). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that "there is no significant relationship between deans' emotional intelligence and head of department academic integrity in Lagos State universities, Nigeria is rejected and an alternate was accepted. The p-value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 significance level which indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implied that a statistically, significant relationship existed between deans' emotional intelligence and head of department academic integrity at Lagos State universities, Nigeria. Suggesting that deans who demonstrated high levels of emotional intelligence may have heads of department who promote academic integrity in the university. The findings are consistent with Martin's (2020) that deans' emotional intelligence is positively related to heads' academic integrity.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the study concluded that faculty Deans who demonstrate authentic leadership behaviour, such as being genuine, honest, transparent and empathetic, are more likely to promote academic integrity among their HODs. The study provides evidence of a positive relationship between Deans' emotional intelligence and the fostering of Heads of departments academic integrity in the state-owned universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. However, the literature review highlights the importance of authentic leadership behaviour in fostering academic integrity among heads of departments in public Universities. The review also suggests that Deans authentic leadership behaviour is a key factor in promoting academic integrity in Lagos State universities. These empirical findings suggest that training Deans on authentic leadership behaviour can promote the academic integrity of teaching and non-teaching staff in the universities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. University authority should develop, promote and communicate clear policies and procedures for academic integrity, including consequences for violations.
2. Faculty Deans should provide leadership training programs that focus on authentic leadership behaviour and promote academic integrity such as workshops, seminars, symposia and conferences on a periodic basis.
3. Deans and Heads of departments should embrace unity and shared responsibility among themselves toward achieving faculty vision, which can help promote academic integrity.
4. The Head of Department should encourage honesty, transparency and originality of academic work to reduce plagiarism and academic dishonesty in research.
5. Faculty Deans should develop emotional intelligence by learning to manage their emotional skills towards achieving academic integrity and university vision.
6. Deans should demonstrate self-discipline, a strong moral code, and a willingness to take risks and be vulnerable.

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